

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The Role of Induced-Pluripotent Stem Cell (iPSC) Model in Untangling the Etiology of Substance Use Disorders: A Scoping Review Protocol

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Supplementary Material 1. Preliminary PubMed search on the topic of iPSC and research areas.

A

Search Strategies (Concept 1 AND Concept 2)		PubMed Search Details					
Concept 1	Concept 2	Search Query	Records(n)				
			1000	2000	3000	4000	5000
iPSC	Cancers	("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("cancer"[Text Word] OR "tumor"[Text Word] OR "malignanc"[Text Word] OR "neoplasm"[Text Word]) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat])			3431		
iPSC	Neurology or neuroscience or neurodegenerative disorders	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("neurology"[Text Word] OR "neuroscienc"[Text Word] OR "neurodegenerative"[Text Word])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))		1561			
iPSC	Personalized or precision medicine	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("personal"[Text Word] OR "precision"[Text Word] OR "personalized medicine"[Text Word])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))		1086			
iPSC	Psychiatric or neuropsychiatric disorders	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("psychiatr"[Text Word] OR "neuropsychiatr"[Text Word] OR "psychiatric disorder"[Text Word] OR "psychiatry"[All Fields])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))		1425			
iPSC	Regenerative medicine	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("regenerative medicine"[Text Word] OR "regeneration"[Text Word] OR "rejuvenation"[Text Word])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))			4257		
iPSC	Substance use disorders: • Substances AND • Addiction OR dependence	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("substance"[Text Word] OR "addict"[Text Word] OR "abuse"[Text Word] OR "dependence"[Text Word] OR "use disorder"[Text Word] OR "alcohol"[Text Word] OR "ethano"[Text Word] OR "cocaine"[Text Word] OR "opioid"[Text Word] OR "smoking"[Text Word] OR "nicotine"[Text Word] OR "cigarette"[Text Word] OR "amphetamin"[Text Word] OR "methamphetamine"[Text Word] OR "marijuana"[Text Word] OR "cannabis"[Text Word])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))		733			
iPSC	SUD: Alcohol/ethanol	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("substance"[Text Word] OR "addict"[Text Word] OR "abuse"[Text Word] OR "dependence"[Text Word] OR "use disorder"[Text Word] OR "alcohol"[Text Word] OR "ethanol"[Text Word])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))		605			
iPSC	SUD: Am-/Metham-phetamine	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("substance"[Text Word] OR "addict"[Text Word] OR "abuse"[Text Word] OR "dependence"[Text Word] OR "use disorder"[Text Word] OR "amphetamin"[Text Word] OR "methamphetamine"[Text Word])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))		439			
iPSC	SUD: Cigarette/nicotine	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("substance"[Text Word] OR "addict"[Text Word] OR "abuse"[Text Word] OR "dependence"[Text Word] OR "use disorder"[Text Word] OR "smoking"[Text Word] OR "nicotine"[Text Word] OR "cigarette"[Text Word])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))		490			
iPSC	SUD: Cannabis	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("substance"[Text Word] OR "addict"[Text Word] OR "abuse"[Text Word] OR "dependence"[Text Word] OR "use disorder"[Text Word] OR "marijuana"[Text Word] OR "cannabis"[Text Word])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))		435			
iPSC	SUD: Cocaine	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("substance"[Text Word] OR "addict"[Text Word] OR "abuse"[Text Word] OR "dependence"[Text Word] OR "use disorder"[Text Word] OR "cocaine"[Text Word])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))		432			
iPSC	SUD: Opioid	((("Induced Pluripotent"[Text Word] OR "IPS"[Text Word] OR "iPSC"[Text Word]) AND ("substance"[Text Word] OR "addict"[Text Word] OR "abuse"[Text Word] OR "dependence"[Text Word] OR "use disorder"[Text Word] OR "opioid"[Text Word])) AND (1991/1/1:2021/12/31[pdat]))		471			

B-1

Preliminary Search Records in PubMed
(on 28 Feb 2022, updated 28 Dec 2022)

B-2

Preliminary Search Records in PubMed
(on 28 Feb 2022, updated 28 Dec 2022)

Supplementary Material 1 summarizes the preliminary search on the topic of **iPSC *and* research areas** from PubMed® (*The United States National Library of Medicine, the National Institutes of Health*) database starting from 1991 to 2021. We examined a total of 12 research areas, comprised of six notable fields (cancers, neurology/neuroscience/neurodegenerative disorders, personalized/precision medicine, psychiatric/neuropsychiatric disorders, regenerative medicine, substance use disorders) and six specific common substance use disorders (alcohol, am-/metham-phethamine, cigarette/nicotine, cannabis, cocaine, and opioid). The search was originally retrieved on 22 February 2022 and updated on 28 December 2022.

Overall, the search results showed that the records of iPSC in each research area started growing after the first human iPSC reprogramming was generated in 2007,¹ and then has become accelerating in various research fields after the clinical iPSC trial was launched in 2014.^{2,3} In our search results, among the six major research areas, the top field was personalized/precision medicine, while the least prevalent was substance use disorders. Moreover, among the six common substances used, the highest number of records was alcohol, followed by cigarette/nicotine. The number of records for substance use disorders, alcohol, and cigarette/nicotine uses were far smaller than the other five research areas. Altogether, this information suggests a plausible conclusion that the iPSC model has been less used in substance use areas than other major research areas, including other psychiatric disorders. Noticeably, among the six common substances used, alcohol and cigarette/nicotine have been the most frequently studied using iPSC approaches.

1A Summary table for the search terms and results.

As this is a preliminary assessment to determine a prospective amount of available literature in our topic of interest, we did a PubMed search using gross search terms as shown in this tableau **Supplementary Material 1A**. **Two concepts** were applied as follows: (i) **concept 1** – ‘iPSC’ (*the 1st column*) **AND** (ii) **concept 2** – ‘research areas’ (*the 2nd column*) with the limited year of publication from 1991 to 2021. Each of the search terms and results for the 12 research areas is presented in each row and grouped by colored according to relevance to a specific substance use disorder: irrelevance (rows 1-6, blue); and relevance (rows 7-12, purple). The search terms and results for each research area are detailed in *the 3rd and 4th columns*, respectively. The search results are presented as the horizontal bars with numbers of search records (*the 4th column*).

1B Scatter plots of the search results.

Scatter plots show the PubMed search results focused on **iPSC *and* research areas** during the publication time period from 1991 to 2021. The graph plots the data by the year of publication (x-axis) against the number of search records (y-axis) published in that year. The line between points displays a trend of records over time (year range: 1991-2021; 31 years). Colors indicate specific research areas.

- **1B-1** The plot represents the PubMed search results for the topic of **iPSC *and* the six main research areas** as follows:
 - Cancers
 - Neurology/neuroscience/neurodegenerative disorders
 - Personalized/precision medicine
 - Psychiatric/neuropsychiatric disorders
 - Regenerative medicine
 - Substance use disorders

- **1B-2** The plot represents the PubMed search results for the topic of **iPSC and the six specific substance use disorders** as follows:
 - Alcohol
 - Am-/Metham-phetamine
 - Cannabis
 - Cigarette/nicotine
 - Cocaine
 - Opioid

iPSC, induced pluripotent stem cell; SUD, substance use disorder.

Supplementary Material 2. Scoping review protocol reporting checklist.

SECTION and Topic	Item #	Checklist item ^a	Section found
ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION			
Title:			
Identification	1a	Identify the report as a protocol of a scoping review	Title
Update	1b	If the protocol is for an update of a previous scoping review, identify as such	NA
Registration	2	If registered, provide the name of the registry (such as JBI) and registration number	Methods: Study protocol
Authors:			
Contact	3a	Provide name, institutional affiliation, e-mail address of all protocol authors; provide physical mailing address of corresponding author	Co-authors' info; Corresponding author's info
Contributions	3b	Describe contributions of protocol authors and identify the guarantor of the review	Author Contributions
Amendments	4	If the protocol represents an amendment of a previously completed or published protocol, identify as such and list changes; otherwise, state plan for documenting important protocol amendments	Methods: Study protocol
Support:			
Sources	5a	Indicate sources of financial or other support for the review	} Funding Disclaimer
Sponsor	5b	Provide name for the review funder and/or sponsor	
Role of sponsor or funder	5c	Describe roles of funder(s), sponsor(s), and/or institution(s), if any, in developing the protocol	
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	6	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known (Note: Consider providing a rationale for the choice of conducting a scoping review as compared to other evidence synthesis approaches)	Study rationale
Objectives	7	Provide an explicit statement of the question(s) the review will address with reference to the inclusion/ exclusion criteria	Methods: Stage I, Review objectives/- questions, para 1-3
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	8	Specify the study characteristics (such as PICO, study design, setting, time frame) and report characteristics (such as years considered, language, publication status) to be used as criteria for eligibility for the review	Methods: Stage I, Inclusion and exclusion criteria
Information sources	9	Describe all intended information sources (such as electronic databases, contact with study authors, trial registers or other grey literature sources) with planned dates of coverage	Methods: Stage II, Sources and types of evidence
Search strategy	10	Present draft of search strategy to be used for at least one electronic database, including planned limits, such that it could be repeated	Methods: Stage II, Search strategy and terms
Study records:			
Data management	11a	Describe the mechanism(s) that will be used to manage records and data throughout the review	Methods: Stage III, Study selection,

			para 1-3
Selection process	11b	State the process that will be used for selecting studies (such as two independent reviewers) through each phase of the review (that is, screening, eligibility and inclusion)	Methods: Stage III, Study selection, para 3-5
Data collection process	11c	Describe planned method of extracting data from reports (such as piloting forms, done independently, in duplicate), any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators	Methods: Stage IV, Data extraction, para 1, 2
Data items	12	List and define all variables for which data will be sought (such as PICO items, funding sources), any preplanned data assumptions and simplifications (Note: Scoping reviews may not use PICO and instead may use JBI's Population, Concept, and Context [PCC] or another approach to reporting eligibility criteria)	Methods: Stage IV, Data extraction, para 1, 3
Outcomes and prioritization	13	List and define all outcomes for which data will be sought, including prioritization of main and additional outcomes, with rationale (Note: Scoping reviews may not extract outcome data, so this can refer to whichever data items are extracted)	Methods: Stage IV, Data extraction, para 3
Risk of bias in individual studies	14	If this is to occur, describe anticipated methods for assessing risk of bias of individual studies, including whether this will be done at the outcome or study level, or both; state how this information will be used in data synthesis (Note: Scoping reviews typically do not include risk of bias assessment, but this information should be described if it will occur)	NA
Data synthesis	15a	Describe criteria under which study data will be presented (Note: Scoping reviews do not typically include quantitative synthesis of study data, but should still describe in advance how extracted data are anticipated to be presented in the resulting review)	Methods: Stage V, Data analysis and presentation, para 1
	15b	Describe the planned approach to how extracted data will be presented (such as figures, tables, evidence gaps maps)	
	15c	Describe any proposed additional analyses (such as thematic analyses) (Note: The JBI methodological guidance does not recommend undertaking thematic analysis as this synthesis of data should ideally occur following methodological appraisal of the included sources)	NA
	15d	If quantitative synthesis is not appropriate, describe the type of summary planned	Methods: Stage V, Data analysis and presentation, para 2
Meta-bias(es)	16	Specify any planned assessment of meta-bias(es) (such as publication bias across studies, selective reporting within studies) (Note: Scoping reviews typically do not include assessment of meta-bias[es], but this information should be described if it will occur)	NA
Confidence in cumulative evidence	17	Describe how the strength of the body of evidence will be assessed (such as GRADE)	NA

* It is strongly recommended that this checklist be read in conjunction with the PRISMA-P Explanation and Elaboration by Shamseer et al.⁵ for important clarification on the items. Amendments to a review protocol should be tracked and dated. The copyright for PRISMA-P (including checklist) is held by the PRISMA-P Group and is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution Licence 4.0.

GRADE, Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation.

NA, Not applicable.

para, paragraph.

Adapted from: Shamseer L, Moher D, Clarke M, et al. PRISMA-P Group. Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation. *BMJ*. 2015;349:g7647. Table 2, PRISMA-P (preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols) 2015 checklist: recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol; p.24. CC BY 4.0.

^aData of checklist *with permission* from: Peters MDJ, Godfrey C, McInerney P, et al. Best practice guidance and reporting items for the development of scoping review protocols. *JBI Evid Synth*. 2022;20(4):953-68. Appendix I, Recommended items to address in a scoping review protocol; p.967-8.

Supplementary Material 2 illustrates a reporting checklist for scoping review protocols. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA-P) checklist^{4 5} was developed to help preparing and reporting of systematic review protocol and also adapted to scoping review protocol. The PRISMA-P 2015 checklist includes 17 main items,⁴ of which some may not be compelled for scoping reviews due to the differences in objectives and methodologies between systematic reviews and scoping reviews. Recently, the PRISMA-P for scoping review protocol was further augmented by the JBI Scoping Review Methodology Group published in 2022.⁶

Here, we reported the recommended items in the protocol based on the guidelines from the PRISMA-P 2015^{4 5} and the JBI 2022.⁶ Checklist items that can be found in our scoping review protocol are listed in the last column, '**Section found**'.

NA, not applicable; para, paragraph.

Supplementary Material 3. Search terms and retrieving results for the topics of iPSC and substance use disorders from the four electronic databases.

A

PubMed.gov

History and Search Details (Searched: 15 April 2022)

Search	Actions	Details	Query	Results
#3	...	>	Search: (#1 AND #2) AND English[lang] AND "Journal Article" [Publication Type] AND ("2007/01/01"[Date - Publication] : "2022/03/31"[Date - Publication])	1,327
#2	...	>	Search: (Substance*[tw] OR Alcohol*[tw] OR ethanol*[tw] OR Narcotic*[tw] OR Cocaine[tw] OR Opioid*[tw] OR amphetamine*[tw] OR meth[tw] OR methamphetamine*[tw] OR marijuana[tw] OR cannab*[tw] OR nicotin*[tw] OR tobacco[tw] OR cigar*[tw] OR Smoke*[tw] OR Smoking[tw] OR Psychoactive[tw] OR psychostimulant*[tw] OR MPTP[tw] OR MDA[tw] OR MDMA[tw] OR Addict*[tw] OR Abus*[tw] OR Habit*[tw] OR Misuse*[tw] OR User*[tw] OR hallucinoge*[tw] OR "illicit drug"*[tw] OR "illegal drug"*[tw] OR depressants[tw])	2,288,622
#1	...	>	Search: ("Induced Pluripotent"*[tw] OR IPS[tw] OR iPSC[tw] OR hiPSC[tw] OR organoid*[tw] OR "pluripotent stem cell"*[tw])	59,063

B

Embase

History Save | Delete | Print view | Export | Email Combine > using And Or (Searched: 4 April 2022) [^ Collapse](#)

<input type="checkbox"/> #4	#3 AND 'article'/it	961
<input type="checkbox"/> #3	#1 AND #2 AND [English]/lim AND [01-01-2007]/sd NOT [01-04-2022]/sd	1,919
<input type="checkbox"/> #2	substance*:ti,ab,kw OR alcohol*:ti,ab,kw OR ethanol*:ti,ab,kw OR narcotic*:ti,ab,kw OR cocaine:ti,ab,kw OR opioid*:ti,ab,kw OR amphetamine*:ti,ab,kw OR meth:ti,ab,kw OR methamphetamine*:ti,ab,kw OR marijuana:ti,ab,kw OR cannab*:ti,ab,kw OR nicotin*:ti,ab,kw OR tobacco:ti,ab,kw OR cigar*:ti,ab,kw OR smoke*:ti,ab,kw OR smoking:ti,ab,kw OR psychoactive:ti,ab,kw OR psychostimulant*:ti,ab,kw OR mptp:ti,ab,kw OR mda:ti,ab,kw OR mdma:ti,ab,kw OR addict*:ti,ab,kw OR abus*:ti,ab,kw OR habit*:ti,ab,kw OR misuse*:ti,ab,kw OR user*:ti,ab,kw OR hallucinoge*:ti,ab,kw OR "illicit drug*":ti,ab,kw OR "illegal drug*":ti,ab,kw OR depressants:ti,ab,kw	2,487,029
<input type="checkbox"/> #1	"induced pluripotent":ti,ab,kw OR ips:ti,ab,kw OR ipsc:ti,ab,kw OR hips:ti,ab,kw OR organoid*:ti,ab,kw OR "pluripotent stem cell*":ti,ab,kw	63,151

C

Clarivate

Web of Science™ (Searched: 4 April 2022)

0/3 Combined Sets Export Clear History

<input type="checkbox"/>	3	(((#2 AND #1) AND DT=(Article)) AND PY=(2007-2022)) AND LA=(English)	1,438	Add to Query	🔗	✎	🔔
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	TS=(Substance* OR Alcohol* OR ethanol* OR Narcotic* OR Cocaine OR Opioid* OR amphetamine* OR meth OR methamphetamine* OR marijuana OR cannab* OR nicotin* OR tobacco OR cigar* OR Smoke* OR Smoking OR Psychoactive OR psychostimulant* OR MPTP OR MDA OR MDMA OR Addict* OR Abus* OR Habit* OR Misuse* OR User* OR hallucinoge*OR "illicit drug*" OR "illegal drug*" OR depressants)	3,733,143	Add to Query	🔗	✎	🔔
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	TS=("Induced Pluripotent" OR IPS OR iPSC OR hiPSC OR organoid* OR "pluripotent stem cell**")	62,668	Add to Query	🔗	✎	🔔

D

Scopus

Search History Saved Searches (Searched: 1 April 2022)

Combined queries >

<input type="checkbox"/>	2	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("induced Pluripotent" OR ips OR ipsc OR hipsc OR organoid* OR "pluripotent stem cell") AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (substance* OR alcohol* OR ethanol* OR narcotic* OR cocaine OR opioid* OR amphetamine* OR meth OR methamphetamine* OR marijuana OR cannab* OR nicotin* OR tobacco OR cigar* OR smoke* OR smoking OR psychoactive OR psychostimulant* OR mptp OR mda OR mdma OR addict* OR abus* OR habit* OR misuse* OR user* OR hallucinoge* OR "illicit drug*" OR "illegal drug*" OR depressants)) AND PUBYEAR > 2006 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "English"))	2,257 results	🔔 Set Alert	⋮ More
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("induced Pluripotent" OR ips OR ipsc OR hipsc OR organoid* OR "pluripotent stem cell") AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (substance* OR alcohol* OR ethanol* OR narcotic* OR cocaine OR opioid* OR amphetamine* OR meth OR methamphetamine* OR marijuana OR cannab* OR nicotin* OR tobacco OR cigar* OR smoke* OR smoking OR psychoactive OR psychostimulant* OR mptp OR mda OR mdma OR addict* OR abus* OR habit* OR misuse* OR user* OR hallucinoge* OR "illicit drug*" OR "illegal drug*" OR depressants)) AND PUBYEAR > 2006	3,426 results	🔔 Set Alert	⋮ More

Supplementary Material 3 displays search terms and retrieving results for the topics of **induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC) and substance use disorders** from the four electronic databases: PubMed® (*The United States National Library of Medicine, the National Institutes of Health*), Embase® (*Elsevier*), Web of Science™ Core Collection (*Science Citation Index Expanded, Social Sciences Citation Index, Arts & Humanities Citation Index, Emerging Sources Citation Index, Conference Proceedings Citation Index, Book Citation Index, and Current Chemical Reactions, Index Chemicus*), and Scopus® (*Elsevier*).

Two concepts were applied: (i) **concept 1 – iPSC:** ("induced pluripotent" OR ips OR ipsc OR hiPSC OR organoid* OR "pluripotent stem cell**") **AND** (ii) **concept 2 – addictive drugs or substances:** (substance* OR alcohol* OR ethanol* OR narcotic* OR cocaine OR opioid* OR amphetamine* OR meth OR methamphetamine* OR marijuana OR cannab* OR nicotin* OR

tobacco OR cigar* OR smoke* OR smoking OR psychoactive OR psychostimulant* OR MPTP OR MDA OR MDMA OR addict* OR abus* OR habit* OR misuse* OR user* OR hallucinoge* OR "illicit drug*" OR "illegal drug*" OR depressants). The search was limited the publication time from 2007 to March 2022. Read more details in the protocol, **Methods**, Stage II: 'Search strategy and terms'.

The search queries and indexed terms were adapted and applied to the search engine of each database shown as follows:

- **3A** PubMed search and results.
- **3B** Embase search and results.
- **3C** Web of Science and results.
- **3D** Scopus search and results.

REFERENCES:

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6. Peters MDJ, Godfrey C, McInerney P, et al. Best practice guidance and reporting items for the development of scoping review protocols. *JBI Evid Synth* 2022;20(4):953-68. doi:10.11124/JBIES-21-00242